

Studies on the Composition and Stability of Chromium Complexes of Amino-acids

A. Aziz Khan and Wahid U. Malik

Composition and stability of a number of complexes of Cr(III) with amino-acids have been studied by spectrophotometric and pH-metric methods. The combining ratio of 1:3, Cr(III): amino-acid, which might vary to 1:2, depending on the concentration of the reactants, has been found to exist in most cases. For methionine and asparagine, the ratios are 1:2 for aspartic acid, and 1:1. β -Alanine forms no violet complex. The results have been explained in the light of the influence of different side groups on the relative position of $-NH_2$ and $-COOH$ groups. Stability constants of the different complexes point towards the similarity in the composition of the Cr(III)-amino-acid complexes.

Basic chromium salts are of considerable importance in tanning industry by virtue of their tendency to form complexes with the collagen molecule or the possibility of their indirect combination with amino-acid residues of the protein. Until recently, little has been done to understand the real nature of the reactions involved and only a few references dealing with the isolation and characterisation of the products of interaction of Cr(III) and amino-acids¹⁻³ are available in the literature. Physico-chemical methods have been scarcely employed and except for the work of Green and Ang⁴, other studies^{5,6} have been of preliminary nature. The authors⁴ investigated comprehensively the reaction between basic chromic chloride and ($\pm$)- α -alanine with the help of spectrophotometric and pH-metric methods and reached some important conclusions about the structure of the product formed on refluxing the reactants for nearly 48 hours.

During the course of our preliminary investigations⁷ on the complexes of Cr(III) with lysine, leucine, and aspartic acid, it was observed that these acids reacted with normal chromic chloride and the reaction reached completion on heating the mixture for about 2 hours at 80° on a water bath (separate experiments showed that constant absorption values are reached in about 50-60 minutes) and that the combining ratio of the reactants was dependent on the concentrations of the amino-acids. It was therefore considered necessary to carry out comprehensive studies on the composition and stability of the complexes formed by the interaction of normal chromic chloride and amino-acids.

1. Teohogoeff and Serbin, *Compt. rend.*, 1910, **151**, 1361.
2. Hugouenng and Morel, *ibid.*, 1912, **154**, 119.
3. Ley and Fickens, *Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 377.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5486.
5. Volshstein, *Acad. Sci. USSR*, 1946, **54**, 321.
6. Shinthleworth, *J. Intern. Leather Traders' Chem.*, 1948, **32**, 116.
7. Khan and Malik, *Curr. Sci.*, 1960, **29**, 135.

EXPERIMENTAL

($\pm$)-Serine, ($\pm$)-lysine, ($\pm$)-methionine (B.D.H.), α -alanine (Eastman and Kodak), ($\pm$)-valine, (-)-arginine hydrochloride, (-)-leucine, and (-)-asparagine (E. Merck) were employed for preparing the solutions. The purity of these acids was tested by chromatography (BuOH:HAc:H₂O as 60:10:20 as solvent and Whatman filter paper No.1 were used and spraying was done with 0.25% ninhydrin solution. In all cases only one spot was obtained). Stock solutions of 0.2*M* were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in 50 ml of double distilled water, with the exception of aspartic acid solution which could not be obtained of concentration greater than 0.02*M* due to its low solubility.

Chromic chloride (0.8 *M*) was prepared by dissolving Baker's Analysed reagent in double distilled water and strength determined volumetrically⁸. KOH and KCl solutions were also prepared from A.R. grade reagents.

Absorption experiments were carried out with a Beckman D.U. spectrophotometer, employing 1-cm Corex cells. Tungsten lamp was used as the source of light. Measurements of pH were carried out with the Cambridge pH-meter, No. L. 269510. Nitrogen (free from CO₂ and O₂) was bubbled to maintain an inert atmosphere. All experiments were carried out at 25° ± 0.1°, using a Townsen and Mercer thermostatic water bath.

Procedure.—Job's method of continued variation was employed for the study of composition of the complexes. Vosburg and Cooper's method⁹ was used for the selection of wave length. The mixtures in different molecular ratios of chromic chloride and amino-acids were mixed and heated for 2 hours. After cooling, the optical densities of these mixtures were measured between 320 m μ and 660 m μ . From the observations it was found that the wave length for maximum absorption varied between 555 m μ and 565 m μ . A mean wave length of 560 m μ was therefore selected for further measurements. For the Job's method, nine test tubes having 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 4.5 ml of amino-acid solution were arranged and chromic chloride solution of the same molecular concentration was added to the respective tubes to make the volume to 5.0 ml. The mixtures were heated on a water bath for 2 hours, cooled, and optical densities were measured at 560 m μ . Optical densities of corresponding concentrations of chromic chloride were also measured at the same wave length.

Measurements of pH for the determination of stability constants were carried out with the same solutions of amino-acids and chromic chloride as given above. Amino-acid solutions (4 ml, 4.8 ml, and 9.6 ml of 0.1*M*) were mixed with 0.8 ml, 1.6 ml, and 2.4 ml of CrCl₃ (0.1*M*) and 1.2 ml, 2.4 ml, and 4.8 ml of CrCl₃ (0.1*M*) respectively. The mixtures were heated till the completion of the reaction. After adding 1.0 *M*-KCl (10 ml), the total volume was made to 25 ml; 20 ml of this solution was taken in the cell. The pH-titrations were carried out using 0.1266*N*-KOH (carbonate-free) added from a microburette.

The results of the spectrophotometric studies are summarised in Table I. The combining ratios, as found from the curves, are also shown in the table.

8. Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis," Vol. I, 5th ed. p. 28.

9. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1941, 63, 437.

TABLE I

Combining ratio of Cr^{3+} -amino-acids from the maxima of absorption curves.

Amino-acid.	Ratio for concentrations.			Ratio for 0.0133 M-CrCl ₃ : 0.04M-acid.
	0.05M.	0.02M.	0.0133M.	
Glycine	1:3	1:2	1:2	1:3
Alanine	1:3	1:2	1:2	1:3
Asparagine	1:2	1:2	1:2	1:2
Serine	1:3	1:3	1:2	1:3
Arginine hydrochloride.	1:3	1:3	1:2	1:3
Leucine	1:3	1:2	1:3	1:2
Methionine	1:2	1:2	1:2	1:2
Lysine	1:3	1:2	1:2	1:3
Valine	1:3	1:2	1:2	1:3
Aspartic acid	..	1:1	1:1	..

DISCUSSION

The structures of the complexes according to the ratios, recorded in Table I, may be shown as:

For ratio 1:2:

For ratio 1:1 (only^o in case of aspartic acid):

More than one structures, including (I), mentioned above, were suggested by Green and Ang^t, but in none of these the role of NH_2 group could be clearly understood. On the other hand, their contention appears to be one of the ineffectiveness of the position of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group in controlling complex-ion formation. To us it appears that $\alpha\text{-NH}_2$ group

of amino-acids is either directly taking part in the complex formation or its vicinity to the carboxylic group helps in allowing the latter to co-ordinate with the metal ion. Our negative results with β -alanine (where no violet colour was obtained on heating with chromic chloride) support this view point. In this compound the $-\text{NH}_2$ group is quite far apart from the α -COOH group, with the result that it does not influence the co-ordination here. Secondly, the presence of NH_2 -CO group (as in the case of asparagine), CH_2 -S-group (in the case of methionine), and -COOH group (in the case of aspartic acid) also affects the ratio of the reactants. The reaction with aspartic acid appears to be different since the ratio 1:1 is realised. Here the structure (III) may be put forward.

pH-metric studies, carried out with mixtures of chromic chloride and amino-acids in the ratio 1:3, also point to the existence of complex ions. When the mixture is titrated with KOH, the solution remains clear up to pH 6 although the violet colour gradually fades to green and after pH 6, the precipitation of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sets in. Thus there is a gradual decomposition of the complex (formed by heating solutions of amino-acids and chromic chloride) during its titration with KOH.

For the determination of stability constants, the procedure of Albert¹⁰ was followed. Formation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against $\log S_c$, where $\bar{n}$ is the number of amino-acid molecules bound per atom of metal and $\log S_c$ is the concentration of the acid present in the complex form. Stepwise stability constants were obtained from the values of $\log c$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5, 1.5$ and 2.5 and the overall stability constants determined from those at $\bar{n} = 1$ and 2 . The values for different amino-acids are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Stability constants of various Cr(III)-amino-acid complexes.

	K_1 .	K_2 .	K_3 .	Ks_1 .	Ks_2 .
Valine	8.3	6.4	5.4	14.5	17.40
Leucine	8.8	6.8	5.9	16.3	19.25
Asparagine	7.7	5.9	4.9	13.8	15.80
Glycine	8.4	6.4	5.7	15.4	17.90
α -Alanine	8.6	6.6	5.6	15.6	17.90
Methionine	8.3	6.2	5.3	14.4	17.00
Serine	8.0	6.2	5.2	14.1	17.10
Lysine	8.1	6.2	5.3	14.3	17.00
β -arginine	8.0	6.1	5.2	13.8	16.80

From the above data it is clear that successive constants as well as the overall stability constants do not vary very much for different amino-acids. The similarity suggests that in these cases the bonding of chromium and amino-acids is of similar nature, a fact confirmed from the absorption data where λ_{max} was found to range between 555 and 565 μ in almost all cases.

Thanks are due to Prof. M. O. Farooq, formerly Head of the Chemistry Department, for the facilities provided to carry out the work and the Ministry of Scientific and Cultural Affairs, Govt. of India, for the award of a scholarship to one of them (A.A.K.).